

ARPA (HORDEUM VULGARE L.) NING UMUMIY AHAMIYATI VA ISTIQBOLLI DONLI EKIN SIFATIDAGI O‘RNI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada arpa (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) ning global oziq-ovqat xavfsizligidagi o‘rni, biologik xususiyatlari, kimyoviy tarkibi hamda istiqbolli donli ekin sifatidagi ahamiyati ilmiy jihatdan tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, arpa yuqori moslashuvchanligi, ozuqaviy qiymati va turli sohalarda keng qo‘llanilishi bilan ajralib turadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Arpa (*Hordeum vulgare* L.), oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi moslashuvchanlik, ozuqaviy qiymat, β -glukan

Аннотация: В данной статье с научной точки зрения анализируется роль ячменя (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) в обеспечении глобальной продовольственной безопасности, его биологические особенности, химический состав и значение как перспективной зерновой культуры. Исследования показывают, что ячмень отличается высокой адаптивностью, питательной ценностью и широким применением в различных отраслях.

Ключевые слова: Ячмень (*Hordeum vulgare* L.), продовольственная безопасность, адаптивность, пищевая ценность, β -глюкан

Abstract: This article provides a scientific analysis of the role of barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) in ensuring global food security, its biological characteristics, chemical composition, and significance as a promising cereal crop. Research shows that barley is distinguished by its high adaptability, nutritional value, and wide application in various industries.

Key words: Barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.), food security, adaptability, nutritional value, β -glucan

Dunyo miqyosida oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi masalasi bugungi kunda eng dolzarb muammolardan biri hisoblanadi. Aholi sonining ortib borishi oziq-ovqat mahsulotlariga bo‘lgan talabni keskin oshirmoqda. Shu sababli yangi va barqaror oziq-ovqat manbalarini izlash zarurati ortmoqda.

Arpa (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) bug‘doy va makkajo‘xori kabi asosiy don ekinlariga nisbatan bir qator afzalliklarga ega bo‘lib, oziq-ovqat, yem-xashak, ichimliklar va sanoat xomashyosi sifatida keng qo‘llaniladi. FAO ma‘lumotlariga ko‘ra, arpa dunyo bo‘ylab 70 million gektar maydonda yetishtiriladi va ishlab chiqarish hajmi bo‘yicha to‘rtinchi o‘rinda turadi [7]. Arpa dunyo bo‘ylab keng tarqalgan va qishloq xo‘jaligining muhim komponenti hisoblanadi. Uning asosiy qo‘llanilish sohasi chorvachilikda yem-xashak sifatida bo‘lsa-da, oziq-ovqat mahsuloti sifatida foydalanish ham ortib bormoqda. Arpa donidan non, yorma va pivo ishlab chiqarishda keng foydalaniladi. Ayniqsa, Osiyo mamlakatlarida, jumladan Xitoy va Yaponiyada, arpa inson iste‘molining muhim qismi hisoblanadi, bu hududlarda iste‘mol qilinadigan arpaning qariyb 80 foizi oziq-ovqat sifatida ishlatiladi [8]. Global ishlab chiqarish hajmi 157 Mt ni tashkil etib, bu dunyo don iste‘molining 15% ga teng [1]. Ushbu ishlab chiqarishning katta qismi chorva ozuqasi va solod ishlab chiqarishga yo‘naltirilgan [16]. So‘nggi ma‘lumotlarga ko‘ra, arpa hosilining 70% dan ortig‘i yem-xashak, 21% sanoat (pivo va distillash), va 6% dan kamrog‘i

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bevosita inson iste'moli uchun ishlatiladi [10]. Arpa yuqori ozuqaviy qiymatga ega bo‘lib, inson salomatligi uchun foydali mahsulot hisoblanadi. Uning tarkibida mavjud β -glukan tolasi qondagi xolesterin darajasini kamaytiradi va ichak faoliyatini yaxshilaydi [13]. Shuningdek, arpa tarkibida antioksidant moddalar mavjud bo‘lib, ular yallig‘lanishga qarshi ta’sir ko‘rsatadi va yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari xavfini kamaytiradi [23]. Arpa mahsulotlari glyukoza darajasini tartibga solish orqali diabet kasalligi xavfini kamaytirishga yordam beradi [24]. Bundan tashqari, arpa tarkibidagi kletchatkalar vaznni kamaytirish, qon bosimini pasaytirish va immun tizimini mustahkamlashda muhim rol o‘ynaydi [12,17]. Arpa qadimiy ekinlardan biri bo‘lib, uning kelib chiqishi Neolit davriga (miloddan avvalgi 7000-yil) borib taqaladi [25]. Madaniy arpa *Hordeum spontaneum* yovvoyi turidan kelib chiqqan bo‘lib, u ilk bor Turkiyada Karl Koch tomonidan tavsiflangan [18]. Arpa Poaceae oilasiga mansub diploid o‘simlik ($2n=14$) bo‘lib, genom hajmi $5,44 \times 10^3$ Mb ni tashkil etadi [5, 20]. U morfologik jihatdan: och yashil barglari, rivojlangan tilcha, boshqoq shaklidagi to‘pguli bilan ajralib turadi. Arpa ikki qatorli (*H. vulgare* ssp. *distichum*) va olti qatorli (*H. vulgare* ssp. *hexastichum*) turlarga bo‘linadi [14, 15]. Arpa eng moslashuvchan donli ekinlardan biri bo‘lib, turli iqlim sharoitlarida yetishtiriladi. Kuzgi arpaning vegetatsiya davri 210–270 kun, bahorgi arpaniki esa 90–150 kunni tashkil etadi [16]. Ushbu ekin qisqa vegetatsiya davri va tez o‘sish xususiyati tufayli noqulay sharoitlarga yaxshi moslashadi [6, 4]. So‘nggi 50 yil davomida hosildorlik 1,4 t/ga dan 3 t/ga gacha oshgan, bu esa seleksiya va agrotexnika yutuqlari bilan izohlanadi. Arpa yetishtirishda Yevropa yetakchi hisoblanadi, undan keyin Osiyo turadi. Yevropa Ittifoqi va Rossiya asosiy ishlab chiqaruvchilar bo‘lib, mos ravishda 58 va 20 Mt dan ortiq hosil yetishtiradi [22]. Germaniya va Fransiya Yevropaning yetakchi ishlab chiqaruvchilari bo‘lib, yuqori hosildorlik ko‘rsatkichlariga ega [22, 23]. Arpa chorvachilik, oziq-ovqat sanoati va bioyoqilg‘i ishlab chiqarishda keng qo‘llaniladi [2].

Arpa donining asosiy qismi (82–85%) urug‘palladan iborat bo‘lib, u quyidagi moddalarni o‘z ichiga oladi: uglevodlar: 70–82%, oqsillar: 10–13%, lipidlar: 2–2,5%, mineral moddalar: 2,7% [9]. Arpa tarkibida β -glukanlar, tokollar va polifenollar mavjud bo‘lib, ular antioksidant va sog‘lomlashtiruvchi xususiyatlarga ega [3]. Don tarkibi genotip va muhit sharoitlariga bog‘liq ravishda o‘zgaradi [20, 11].

Xulosa qilib aytganda, arpa global oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta’minlashda muhim o‘rin tutuvchi istiqbolli donli ekin hisoblanadi. Uning yuqori moslashuvchanligi, ozuqaviy qiymati va keng qo‘llanilish imkoniyatlari uni kelajakda strategik ekin sifatida ahamiyatini yanada oshiradi. Shu sababli arpa yetishtirishni kengaytirish va uning genetik salohiyatini chuqur o‘rganish dolzarb vazifalardan biri hisoblanadi.

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